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Mov10 activation in the large intestine in Crohn's.

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Tissue-specific activation of RISC complex components in human disease is not widely understood. We report activation of MOV10 in the large intestines of humans with Crohn's Disease. The increase in message for MOV10 RISC helicase in the colon in IBD (CD) was larger than nearly all genes measured in the transcriptome. Aberrant RNAi function is either a symptom of or an etiologic contributor to inflammation in IBD.